

**IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE PROSECUTOR'S
SUPERVISION OVER THE PREVENTION OF CORRUPTION IN
GENERAL SECONDARY, SECONDARY SPECIAL, AND PROFESSIONAL
EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS**

Munira Kurbanovna Bobomarova

Independent researcher of The Supreme School OF Judges

Tel: +998 90 960 98 89

Аннотация. Мазкур тезисда умумий ўрта, ўрта махсус ва профессионал таълим муассасаларида коррупцияга қарши курашишга оид қонунчилик ижроси устидан прокурор назорати самарадорлигини ошириш бўйича бир қатор таклифлар хорижий амалиёт ва тажрибага асосланган ҳолда келтириб ўтилган.

Калит сўзлар: коррупция, прокурор назорати, прокуратура органлари, вояга етмаганлар, таълим муассасалари.

Аннотация. В этом тезисе на основе зарубежной практики и опыта представлен ряд предложений по повышению эффективности прокурорского надзора за исполнением законодательства о противодействии коррупции в учреждениях общего среднего, среднего специального и профессионального образования.

Ключевые слова: коррупция, прокурорский надзор, прокуратура, несовершеннолетние, образовательные учреждения.

Abstract. In this thesis, several suggestions on improving the effectiveness of the prosecutor's control over the implementation of legislation on combating corruption in general secondary, secondary special and professional educational institutions are presented based on foreign practice and experience.

Key words: corruption, prosecutor's supervision, prosecutor's office, minors, educational institutions.

In recent years, important organizational and legal reforms have been implemented in the field of fighting corruption in our country. Systematic measures are being taken to increase the legal consciousness and culture of the population, to form an intolerant attitude against corruption in the society.

Creating a corruption-free society and state will be a solid guarantee of the country's development. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his speech at the ceremony dedicated to the 26th anniversary of our Constitution on December 7, 2018, stated "We will never achieve our goals with corruption"[1].

The state is implementing all the anti-corruption reforms for the rights and interests of citizens.

Special attention is being paid to the training of independent thinking, high moral and ethical qualities, and competitive personnel by forming an uncompromising attitude towards corruption, especially in the field of education.

During the next three years, more than 200 legal documents related to the field of education were adopted. As a result of these measures, the level of coverage of young people with higher education increased from 9% to 20%. The amount of funds allocated to the field from the budget is increasing, and the salaries of professors and teachers are being increased year by year. Of course, education is an important area in the fight against corruption. Because it is the final stage of continuous education that provides a path to work.

As a continuation of the reforms, in order to set priorities for the systematic reform of general secondary and extracurricular education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, to raise the spiritual, moral and intellectual development of the young generation to a new level in terms of quality, to introduce innovative forms and methods of education into the educational process, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Decree No. PF-5538 dated September 5, 2018 "On additional measures to improve the management system of public education" was signed, accepting children to general education institutions, as well as eliminating elements of various forms of corruption in the

educational process, an effective mechanism for fighting corruption in the public education system the goals of creation and creation of a modern system of payment for labour and social security of civil servants, which allows to increase the attractiveness of public service in the public education system, reduce the risk of corruption and abuse of office, were determined.

It is appropriate to put forward the opinion that "the prosecutor's office is responsible for investigating cases of corruption in educational institutions."

We can see this in:

First, it involves examining financial transactions, contracts and other activities to identify signs of bribery, embezzlement, nepotism or other corrupt acts or omissions in the industry. After gathering evidence, prosecutors file charges and take cases to court, demanding accountability for those involved in corruption.

Second, the prosecutor's office provides legal guidance and advice to educational institutions on anti-corruption measures and public policy issues. This may include recommendations for establishing internal controls, whistleblower protection mechanisms and effective systems to prevent and detect corruption.

Third, prosecutors work closely with law enforcement agencies to share information and coordinate efforts to investigate corruption cases. This cooperation increases the efficiency of anti-corruption measures and ensures comprehensive and impartial investigation of cases.

Fourthly, one of the most important tasks of prosecutors in this field is the recovery of assets by prosecutors in cases of misappropriation of funds in educational institutions. They work to identify and recover assets obtained through corrupt means, and to ensure that ill-gotten gains are returned to their rightful owners or the state.

In general, the prosecution plays an important role in ensuring high standards of transparency, accountability and integrity in educational institutions. By actively investigating and prosecuting cases of corruption, they contribute to creating an environment that can be the backbone of educational development and community development.

The analysis shows that we believe that the organization and implementation of the prosecutor's control over the execution of legislation in the field of combating corruption is one of the important directions of the activities of state bodies, in particular, the prosecutor's office.

In our opinion, it is necessary to make a number of changes and additions to the current legislation of Uzbekistan in order to use the potential of the prosecutor's control institution over the execution of legislation in the field of combating corruption.

Thus, Article 9 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Combating Corruption" dated January 3, 2017 defines the powers of the General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of combating corruption[2]. In order to expand these powers, it is proposed to state this article of the Law in the following manner.

"Article 9. Powers of the General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the fight against corruption

The General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan within its powers: participates in the development and implementation of state programs and other programs in the field of combating corruption;

supervises the clear and uniform implementation of the anti-corruption legislation and is subordinate to the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and accountable to the chambers of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the results of activities in this field...".

Also, in Article 4 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Prosecutor's Office" dated August 29, 2001, the prosecutor's office has the following main directions: ministries, state committees, agencies, citizens' self-government bodies, public associations, enterprises, institutions, organizations, governors and control over the implementation of laws by other officials, control over the implementation of laws aimed at ensuring the rights and freedoms of citizens, participation in law-making activities and raising legal culture in society, etc., but the control mechanism is not regulated.

In addition, in accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Combating Corruption", the General Prosecutor's Office is designated as a constitutional body engaged in the implementation of the function of monitoring the clear and uniform execution of legislation in the field of combating corruption.

Accordingly, it is proposed to use foreign experience in this regard, taking into account the possibility of certain difficulties related to the issues of ensuring the independence of the relevant structural branches of the General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of fighting corruption.

In particular, in the conditions of Uzbekistan, it is appropriate to establish an independent separate service of special prosecutors who will supervise the clear and uniform implementation of anti-corruption laws.

In this regard, the experience of the Republic of Kazakhstan, one of our closest neighbours, can be a clear example for us.

Article 37, Part 4 of the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On the Prosecutor's Office" dated June 30, 2017, the regulation "On the General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Kazakhstan" approved by the decision of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan No. 563 dated October 13, 2017 "On certain issues of the Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Kazakhstan" with the regulation on the service of special prosecutors of the General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Kazakhstan was developed and put into practice [3].

Also, based on the recommendations of the OECD[4], in order to strengthen control over the clear and uniform execution of legislation in the field of fighting corruption, we believe that it is necessary to organize prosecutors who carry out special control in this field on the basis of departments for coordination of measures to fight against organized crime and corruption. .

In the results of the research, it can be concluded that

Firstly, in order to strengthen the institution of the prosecutor's control over the implementation of legislation in the field of combating corruption, it is proposed to define the directions of the prosecutor's control over the implementation of legislation

in the field of combating corruption, the mechanisms of implementation of control, and the powers of the prosecutor in the implementation of control.

Secondly, based on the recommendations of international organizations such as the UN, the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, the World Bank, and Transparency International, internal control mechanisms over the implementation of departmental measures, including general secondary, secondary special and professional education, should be established to identify areas that are more prone to corruption. in the field of anti-corruption compliance control, and in the public sector, it is proposed to strengthen the public integrity system and reduce the discretionary powers of officials.

Thirdly, it is proposed to supplement the third section "Prosecutor control" of the Law "On Prosecutor's Office" dated August 29, 2001, with a new chapter "Control of clear and uniform implementation of legislation in the field of combating corruption".

Fourth, to identify the areas most prone to corruption, to properly regulate the issues of reporting and resolving conflicts of interest of employees in the performance of their official duties, as well as to strengthen the responsibility for violations of these obligations, corruption by all levels of state bodies, as well as local state authorities. it is suggested that it is necessary to develop measures to determine violations, as well as the reasons and conditions of their occurrence, to strengthen internal control mechanisms over the implementation of departmental measures.

References:

[1] Мирзиёев Ш.М, Ўзбекистон Республикаси Конституциясининг 26 йиллигига бағишланган тантанали маросимдаги маъруза, 2018 йил 7 декабрь // [Электрон манба]: [http:// газета.uz](http://газета.uz). (мурожаат вақти: 10.03.2023 й.).

[2] Закон Республики Узбекистан № ЗРУ-419 «О противодействии коррупции» от 3 января 2017 года// Национальная база данных законодательства, 16.01.2019 г., № 03/19/516/2484; 24.05.2019 г., № 03/19/542/317, 2019 г., № 2, ст. 47)

[3][Electronicresource]:<http://prokuror.gov.kz/rus/o-prokurature/prikazy-generalnogo-prokurora/2019/polozhenie-o-sluzhbe-specialnyh-prokurorov>. (application time: 12.05.2023.).

[4] Сеть по борьбе с коррупцией для стран Восточной Европы и Центральной Азии. Антикоррупционные реформы в Узбекистане. 4-й раунд мониторинга в рамках Стамбульского плана действий по борьбе с коррупцией. ОЭСР, 2019. – С. 266